

Deliverable 6.1

Project Website

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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This document provides details of the website deployed by the Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation (GREAT) project partners to engage stakeholders, raise awareness and leverage the project outcomes, outputs, findings and results.
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List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CMS	Content Management System
DNS	Domain Name System
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
GREAT	Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation
H2020	Horizon 2020 program of the European Union
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
JSX	JavaScript XML
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation

1. Executive Summary

This document provides details of the website deployed by the Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation (GREAT) project partners in order to engage stakeholders, raise awareness and leverage the project outcomes, outputs, findings and results. The purpose of this deliverable is to present the functionalities of the website in order to support the dissemination, exploitation and sustainable activities of the GREAT project. The website contains the following:

- Partner information
- Project background and objectives
- Regular updates via blogs
- Links to social media channels (for example, LinkedIn and Twitter)
- Links to our published academic papers
- Public Relations and articles (upcoming)
- Podcast (upcoming)
- Cycle results/data (upcoming)
- Games for visitors to play (upcoming)
- Contact information for visitors wishing to engage with the GREAT project

Sections marked as 'upcoming' will be completed when further requirements details and content formats are known. The website will be an important vehicle for the whole project duration as well as its sustainability (i.e., 3 years beyond the end of the project), as it forms a public-facing platform to enable the project team to reach and engage key stakeholders, thus ensuring the visibility of the project's actions, activities, outcomes, research findings, and events.

The management of the website and content schedule/consistency will be managed by Playmob. However, in order to ensure an equal representation and share of perspectives across academic and commercial partners with different strengths and discipline focuses, consortium members will have varying levels of access to the website content management system (CMS) and corresponding social media channels. For example, the GREAT project's technical partners and main project manager have full CMS administrative access as well as tailored access to add blog posts or update curated content (e.g., links, publications, events). This will be made available to other interested members for further contributing to the website.

At the project consortium bi-weekly meeting, future key content for the website will be discussed and content will be created following the strategic direction of the project. The website will exist for three years after the end of the project and where relevant, post-project updates of any key outcomes derived from the results findings will be updated on the website.

2. Functionalities of the Project Website

This document provides an overview of the functionalities of the project website. The website will expand during the course of the project to incorporate, for example, the release of new game builds and publications. All functionalities exist as a core design to the website, however, if no content is available for that particular section, it will not be visible yet. A version of the GREAT project website as it was launched on 31 July 2023 is available at <https://greatproject.gg>. The website displays information for the general public including those interested in the project's development. It also acts as a repository for the project's activities, information, tools and progress, and sharing key lessons learnt and enabling others to utilize and replicate our results findings.

Visual 1. Website Homepage

GREAT About Blog Publications Links @ RSS in Twitter

GREAT: Games Realising Effective & Affective Transformation

Research and innovation in the GREAT project will generate new knowledge of the actual and potential impact of games on European society and new understandings of the innovative uses of games to support the social engagement of citizens. Leveraging the central role of games in contemporary culture, it combines academic studies and practical experimentation with novel applications of games.

The GREAT Project aims to demonstrate that games have a positive impact on social engagement and create a new form of dialogue between citizens and policy stakeholders. By exploring the innovative potential of a games, citizens will be able to express their preferences and attitudes on policy issues. The project will carry out a series of case studies to test the approach, investigate its potential, and generalize the results.

Using collaborative design and citizen science methods, it brings together researchers with expertise in the areas of games, data analytics, and policy in an integrated investigation, articulated by case studies of the use of games in facilitating dialogue between citizens and policy stakeholders (policy makers, policy implementers, political parties, campaigning organisations and affected citizens).

The context for the research is the climate emergency, and each case study is a research cycle addressing a policy issue and research questions, with multiple pilots and quantitative and qualitative research activities. An important aspect of the method is to place games in an authentic context, so that players are aware that their activities have real-world implications, and to close the loop by including interactions with policy stakeholders.

Visual 2. Website – 'About' Section

DIPF
 Leibniz-Institut für Bildungsforschung
 und Bildungsinformation

Leibniz Institute for Research and Information in Education

The Educational Technologies at DIPF (EduTech @ DIPF) is an interdisciplinary and multinational research group, which brings together technical and social disciplines such as information, computer and engineering science, but also pedagogy, didactics and psychology to innovate education. It focuses on Learning Analytics, Personalisation Technologies and Educational Data Mining. Since 2017, the EduTech @ DIPF team has implemented 18+ European- and German-funded projects, and provides supervision to 12+ research candidates.

EduTech belongs to the [Leibniz Institute for Research and Information in Education \(DIPF\)](#). It is a public research organization delivering empirical educational research, digital infrastructure, targeted knowledge transfer and strategies for coping with challenges in education. The institute works closely together with national and international partners. In many cooperations, DIPF acts as the leading coordinator, for example, the German Education Server and Portal, Research Data Education Alliance and Open Educational Resources Information Centre.

As the coordinating institution, DIPF is primarily involved in project management and also has analytics and pedagogical expertise. DIPF will be involved in the data analysis of the data generated by the games.

Project members

- [Hendrik Drachslers](#) (Lead)
- [Dana Kube](#) (Researcher)
- [Jane Yau](#) (Project Manager)

Visual 3. Consortium Partner Entry – 'About' section

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Visual 4. The index page of blog posts

Visual 5. An example of a project blog post

3. Website as a vehicle to meet project KPIs

As per the project grant agreement, the following is in-progress and will be achieved:

- A website is set up as a first action and launched in month 6. It will be regularly updated, including press releases, newsletters and social media updates, and all project-related materials and outputs, and will feature blog posts, interviews, a podcast and other compelling content. KPI (key performance indicators) by the end of GREAT: 100000 unique visitors.
- A quarterly newsletter will be created, summarising project progress and other relevant news, made available on the website and pushed by email subscription.
- Research publications generated will be listed and updated as work progresses (including bibliographic listings). A page of relevant work by other researchers will also be maintained, to enable the website to be used as a hub for researchers interested in its themes.
- A toolkit will be provided and presented via the website to enable others to replicate our project approach, reaching a broad and diverse audience and geographic location. This will evolve from a website hosting project information to a full repository of information, data and tools developed during the project lifetime.
- The project will further ensure all documents, media, code, data and project-specific game instances be made freely available as open-source documents under the Creative Commons 4.0 licence in the website repository. This material will be made accessible via a link from the website, which will be maintained for a minimum of three years following the end of the project.

4. Website Design - Best Practices

The website is designed with modern best practices for web design and development. The following list of best practices has been incorporated into the website design from the outset:

- Responsive design for mobile, tablet and desktop resolutions.
- Fast loading for visitors with less bandwidth.
- Search Engine Optimization (SEO) for organic search engine discoverability.
- Accessibility support, including colour/contrast, alt text for media embeds and keyboard support for navigation/forms.
- Data privacy compliance with GDPR and other applicable regulations.
- Hosting management for long-term reliability upon project completion.

- Intuitive navigation that encourages access to the rest of the site from any page
- Scalable content hierarchy that can handle content growth without a large re-design or new development midway through the project.
- Maintainability through a Content Management System (CMS).
- Built with standard tools and services to avoid accruing 'technical debt'.
- Documentation for its technical implementation and publishing workflows.

5. Structure of the Website

- *Home page*: Brief introduction of the project, partner logos, most recent blog posts, attended events and other releases (such as project video).
- *Blog*: Individual blog posts with permalinks, formatted content, images and embedded multimedia support. Category-based index pages.
- *About*: Currently a section on the 'About' page that lists each partner with their area of expertise and how they contribute to the project, along with a list of their members that are involved.
- *Publications*: A master page to list downloads of published content as PDFs or other file formats including white papers and insight reports (e.g., Zenodo).
- *Press Releases (Upcoming)*: Once press releases are available, this will be a category under the blog with a category-based index page.
- *Contact option*: A simple, public email address in the header that can be upgraded to a contact form as the volume of contact requests becomes larger.
- *Newsletter signup*: A form accessible from the homepage for newsletter signup.
- *Event Page*: A list of events that GREAT project partners are attending/speaking at or are otherwise of interest to the project.
- *Tools / data releases*: Depending on the number of releases, a general-purpose publications page may also link to additional releases such as tools and datasets.
- *Common page footer*: Contains Horizon Europe and UKRI funding attributions and updated in the future as other legal notices become required by law. No personal data is stored or processed, nor are cookies used at launch. Therefore, currently a GDPR notice or cookie banner is not required.

6. Technical providers of the Website

The website uses a combination of technical providers to enable the project team to fulfil the elements required to host, update and populate the site:

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- *Domain name registrar*: InterNetX GmbH (<http://www.internetx.com>) via DIPF
- *Hosting*: Vercel (<https://vercel.com>)
- *DNS provider*: Vercel
- *Git repository*: GitHub (<https://github.com/GreatProjectGG/greatproject.gg> (site), <https://github.com/GreatProjectGG/greatproject-cms> (CMS))
- *Newsletter*: Brevo (<https://www.brevo.com>)
- *Website statistics*: Plausible Analytics (<https://plausible.io>)
- *Email aliases*: <https://improvmx.com>
- *Content Management System (CMS)*: Sanity (<https://sanity.io>)
- *Google Performance*: Google Search Console

The website was built using the Astro framework (<https://astro.build>) using JSX components and JavaScript. A git repository to the main branch will trigger a redeploy with the latest content, via Vercel Git integration. The CMS can also trigger a redeploy.

The website is 'statically built' at deploy time to load faster without using a large amount of JavaScript or relying on a database server for live traffic. During deployment, most content is loaded from the Sanity CMS 'data lake' and subsequently used in .astro pages and JSX components to build static HTML pages.

7. Third Party Services - Costs

Some tools are used under their free tiers as of July 2023. Where required, Playmob will pay in advance for these services and then be reimbursed subsequently.

Hosting: Pro Tier on Vercel for US\$20 per month. Pro tier required due to git integration limitations with GitHub organisations on their free tier.

Newsletter: Currently on the free tier with unlimited contacts, however, there is a 300 emails per day sending limit. Next tier up would be £16 per month for 20,000 emails per month with no daily limit.

Website statistics: Plausible Analytics: £9 per month for 10,000 page views, £19 per month for 100,000 page views.

CMS: On a free Sanity CMS tier currently. The website is statically built, and Sanity does not host many of our resources, therefore this would be sufficient in the meantime. Beyond that, they have very reasonable per usage pricing for extra Content Delivery Network (CDN) bandwidth.

Domain name registration (managed via DIPF): The cost for the first year was €79,80 and then €114 for each subsequent year. Set to auto-renew until 2029 (project length + 3 years as per grant).

8. Conclusion

As presented in this document, the website for the GREAT project has multiple objectives. First, to attract, engage and retain key stakeholders to the project, while enabling the consortium to build up a list of interested stakeholders to provide feedback and subsequently be potential partners with regards to the exploitation of the project results. Second, the website acts as a platform to contain all project information and updates for stakeholders and the public to stay informed of project progress as well as dissemination and communication activities. Finally, to contain all resources, from publications, to data and games, which can be shared, learned from and leveraged to build upon, and keep enhancing the innovation being created.

Annex

User Guide for Project Administrators

1. Content Management System

Due to the large number of the consortium members in the project with varying levels of knowledge of website deployment, the Sanity content management system (CMS) was chosen to allow adding, or updating content over the long lifespan of the project. This allows all consortium members to update publications, list events or change the content of the homepage without any required technical expertise.

Visual 6. An example of a blog post being added via the Content Management System

GREAT Project Site Search [Cmd | K] [JS]

GREAT Project Presentations at International Conference of Young Scientists, 2023 Latest version

Title

GREAT Project Presentations at International Conference of Young Scientists, 2023

Slug
This is the URL path of the blog post

great-project-presentations-at-international-conference-of-young

Categories

- Events
- Project Update

Author
Post attribution. Leave blank to use generic 'GREAT Project' name.

Jane Yau

Summary
Shown in the blog post grid and used for Open Graph (social media) metadata. Recommended 1-2 short to medium sized sentences.

Dissemination activities were underway at the event held in conjunction with the Global Young Academy Annual General Meeting, Kigali, Rwanda, 5-9 June, 2023.

Visual 7. Creating a blog post via the Content Management System

2. Creating a blog post

The body of the blog posts support basic formatting and HTML links with image embedding. In order to allow a specific consortium member to publish their own blog, the "Add an author" (from the Members list) was created.

The 'summary' field is used for social media link previews, Search Engine Optimization (SEO) and in post grids on the blog index or homepage.

The 'slug' is also required and used in the post URL. Simply click 'generate' after adding a blog post title to create it.

Optional banner images that will appear at the top of the blog post page should be in a 2.4:1 aspect ratio and at least 1200x500 pixels in size. Upcoming posts can be scheduled via the content pipeline sheet.

3. Managing partner descriptions

The CMS defines members linked to partner organisations. These can be used for blog post attribution or be listed next to partners on the 'About' page.

Once defined in the CMS, a member's name will be linked to the relevant social media account or homepage from blog posts that they are linked to and on the 'About' page's partner section. A toggle exists to disable listing a member under the partner section. Non-consortium member organisations can be added as Partners as well by deselecting the 'Is Consortium Member?' option. These will not be listed on the 'About' page's partner list. A person can then be linked to this new organisation and used as an author of a guest post on the blog.

4. Adding a Publication

Publications are managed via the CMS and can be uploaded as a single file (e.g., a PDF) directly via the CMS or added as a link to an external source. Each publication is associated with exactly one category (e.g., white paper or insight report). On the *Publications* page, they are grouped by this category and sorted by a published date.

5. Adding an Event

Events are managed via the CMS and have a name, location, event page URL, optional start/end date (or only a start date) and a description field that can be used to add information concerning why this event is relevant to the GREAT Project. An event can tag one or more consortium members that are attending, in which case these will be listed on the events page.

6. Adding a Link

Links are managed via the CMS and they have a title, URL, description and belong to exactly one category. They are primarily intended to point to relevant work by other researchers and are divided into categories that can cover other scopes too. Links can be repositioned into a preferred order via the CMS.

7. Featuring items on the homepage

The CMS controls which blog posts, events, publications or links appear on the homepage as featured items. Existing items can be added to the Featured items list and repositioned in the desired order in order for items to be published and deployed.

Show Featured Items
Show recent items (Publications, Events, Post, Links) marked as 'featured' under recent blog posts.

Featured Items Header

Featured Content

Items
Featured items to show on the homepage.

- The GREAT Project – A pathway to sustainable impact ...
url in Conference Papers
- GREAT Project kick-off meeting
Mar 04 '23 as Jane Yau

+ Add item

Visual 8. Feature items on the Website Homepage

'Show Featured Items' can be deselected in order to disable showing any featured items and the header of this section can be edited too. Events, publications and links appear with a 'short description' field, which can be used as a summary in the featured 'Card' UI. Featured items will appear under the recent blog posts list:

Latest Blog Posts

Global Young Academy Magazine
Posted Jul 25 '23 in Press Coverage
Explore the transformative potential of innovative technologies in education, gender equality, and climate action through Dr. Jane Yau's article in the Global Young Academy's Connections Magazine,...

UN SDG and Games for Change Summit
Posted Jul 18 '23 in Events, Games
Jude Ower, Founder and CEO of Playmob presented at the first ever SDG and G4C (Games for Change) Summit, held at the United Nations HQ on 17th July 2023.

Featured Content

The GREAT Project – A pathway to sustainable impact on climate change policy
Published Apr 05 '23 in Conference Papers
In this paper the authors introduce the EU funded Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation (GREAT) research project.

GREAT Project kick-off meeting
Posted Mar 04 '23 in Project Updates
A fruitful and successful kick-off meeting for the GREAT project (Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation, co-funded by EU and UKRI) with all consortium partners was held on 1-...

Visual 9. Featured items and content

8. Updating the content of the website

The content of the website can be edited from the Sanity CMS without any web design or development expertise. The website content consists of collections of certain types (blog posts, partners, members, socials, navigation menu entries, events, publications, links and categories) and settings pages that apply to a specific page or the website as a whole (site settings, blog settings and the Homepage, About, Events, Publications and Links pages).

Combined, they allow for flexible management of text blocks, list entries, page headers/titles, site navigation, SEO metadata, footer funding attributions and more. Editing content in the CMS only updates the related content in the database and does not automatically update the live site (which requires deployment to take place). Therefore, in the CMS, the 'Deploy' option must be selected (triangular icon) from the navigation bar and then the green 'Deploy' button for the 'live' site should be clicked. This initiates a re-deployment of the entire website on the Vercel hosting provider, taking approximately a minute. In case of errors, view the Vercel deployment logs.

Visual 10. Demonstration of deployment required for website updates

9. Previewing content updates before publishing

It is possible to preview the website prior to deployment by visiting <https://preview.greatproject.gg/> after triggering a deploy via the separate entry for the preview site in the CMS deploy section.

Note that both the actual and preview websites share the same 'dataset', which could lead to preview content being made live by simultaneous edits.

Alternatively, blog posts can initially be posted via the 'Is Hidden?' option when composing a post in the CMS. Once deployed, these will not appear in any post grids (i.e., the homepage, blog or category lists of posts), but available to the visitors, who have the direct URL. The latter approach has the advantage of being able to circumvent the final URL post, so third parties involved in reviewing a blog post do not end up promoting a preview URL, until the post is live. At the source code level, committing to the 'preview' branch currently triggers a deployment to the preview URL.

10. Accessing the website source-code

The site is in a private GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/GreatProjectGG/greatproject.gg> under the 'GreatProjectGG' GitHub organisation. Access may be granted upon discussion with Playmob.

11. Subscribing to newsletters via email

Newsletters are managed by Brevo. The iframe snippet from Brevo to insert the newsletter form onto the homepage can also be managed from the CMS, if it requires updating. Change the iframe dimensions provided by Brevo to 640x400 to fit with the website layout.

12. Accessing website tools

The accounts to third party services (stats, newsletter) are set up with strong and randomised passwords. Playmob and DIPF can grant access to members as required.

13. Viewing of website statistics

Website statistics are tracked in a GDPR compliant manner and without cookies, via Plausible Analytics. Monthly aggregated statistics as well as KPIs will be recorded and stored internally.

14. Receiving 'contact' emails from website users

contact@greatproject.gg is the email address used in the website header. Current consortium members can be added to this via Playmob.

15. Modifying @greatproject.gg email aliases

Email aliases are managed via ImprovMX.

16. Posting content on social media

The Twitter account is set up with access for multiple members. Twitter content can also be scheduled to be posted at a later stage via www.Buffer.com. Note that logging into Twitter from a new country may trigger a verification code email.

The LinkedIn group is moderated and content can be posted/approved by an admin (currently Jude and Joost at Playmob, Jane at DIPF, Simon at SGI). Contact Playmob or Jane for access.

17. Email Aliases

To avoid an individual partner's email address becoming a single point of failure, bespoke email aliases are used wherever possible for different accounts:

- Billing alerts: Implemented where available, currently only Vercel.
- Third party services logins
- Domain name registration
- Social media logins for Twitter: Members: Joost Schuur, Jane Yau, Paul Hollins, Jude Ower.
- General contact emails: contact@greatproject.gg Members: Joost Schuur, Jane Yau

